

Enhancing salinity stress tolerance in corn salad (*Valerianella locusta* L.) through melatonin or salicylic acid-functionalized chitosan seed priming: A smart delivery approach

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ABSTRACT

Soil salinity represents a significant environmental stressor that impairs crop production and yield. A wide range of treatments have been used to reduce the effects of salinity in plants. Among the treatments used, functionalized nanoparticles (NPs) have shown great results. In light of recently demonstrated beneficial effects of chitosan-melatonin nanoparticles (CTS-Mel NPs) and chitosan-salicylic acid nanoparticles (CTS-SA NPs) in mitigating the deleterious consequences of major stress factors and boosting secondary metabolite biosynthesis, the current study aimed to investigate their potential as seed priming coatings to enhance plant performance under both control and salinity stress conditions. For this purpose, CTS (0.1% w/v), Mel (50 μM), SA (0.5 mM), CTS-Mel NPs and CTS-SA NPs were applied as seed priming agents on corn salad (*Valerianella locusta*) seeds, and subsequently key morphophysiological and biochemical properties were assayed under salinity conditions (0, 30 and 60 mM NaCl). Accordingly, salinity stress caused significant reduction in fresh and dry weights (FW and DW) of leaves, chl *a*, total chl, SPAD and enhancement in content of proline, phenolics, MDA, as well as protein content, and activities of SOD and CAT antioxidant enzymes. Concerning the phenolic compounds analyzed, salinity stress did not affect the dominant phenolic constituents with the exception of naringine. Regarding the protective effects of the various priming treatments, the adverse effects of salinity stress were ameliorated with the application of most of the applied treatments, and with CTS-Mel NPs in particular, by enhancing biomass, pigments, total phenols, protein, SOD and CAT antioxidant enzymatic activities, as well as the content of some dominant constituents of phenolic profile. CTS-Mel NPs enhanced chlorogenic acid, naringine, o-coumaric acid and catechin hydrate under both control and salinity conditions. Overall, CTS-Mel NPs outperformed CTS-SA NPs as a seed priming coating and could potentially be widely introduced as an innovative, sustainable approach to mitigate the effects of salinity and other abiotic stress conditions in crop plants.

1. Introduction

Salinity has a detrimental effect on various plant processes, with the effects being most pronounced at the initial stages of seed germination and continuing up to the final stages of growth and development. Corresponding to the changes in the primary and secondary metabolism of plants that suffer from salt stress, the growth and performance of plants

are generally delayed, as reported in a large number of plant species (Wani et al., 2020; Filippou et al., 2021; Mohammadi et al., 2021; Raza et al., 2023). In plant metabolism, increased production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) is one of the most common consequences of stress and their excessive accumulation leads to the induction of oxidative stress. In addition, salinity causes osmotic stress due to the imbalance of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions (Hasanuzzaman et al., 2020). Considering the effects of

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salinity, it can be postulated that sensitive plant species may be unable to reach their genetic potential for production. In order to survive, plants use a variety of defense strategies. For example, increases in phenolic compounds, polyamines and antioxidant enzymatic activities are generally observed in plants subjected to salinity stress (Antoniou et al., 2021; Gohari et al., 2023a, 2023b).

However, to buffer or mitigate the negative effects of salinity, smart approaches such as nanotechnology-based chemical priming techniques, have shown promising results (Ioannou et al., 2020; Spanos et al., 2021; Gohari et al., 2024). As reported and evidenced in a wide range of studies, priming may be an efficient strategy for managing stress conditions prior to stress onset, as it can facilitate the activation of defensive mechanisms and physiological tolerance (Savvides et al., 2016; Antoniou et al., 2020; Gohari et al., 2024). Concerning the priming agents, a wide range of compounds, including proline, melatonin, glycine-betaine, and chitosan, have been successfully employed to augment plant performance (e.g. Antoniou et al., 2017; Gohari et al., 2021). Such agents can be combined with NP as a unique feature of nanotechnology to enhance plant tolerance to different stress conditions, as in the case of previous works (Gohari et al., 2021, 2023b).

Chitosan (CTS) is a natural biopolymer that exhibits a range of distinctive properties, including hydrophilicity, polycationicity, biocompatibility, degradability, non-toxicity, and antimicrobial activity (Verlee et al., 2017; Mujtaba et al., 2020), while the beneficial effects of chitosan have been demonstrated on a range of plant processes (Wang et al., 2015; Saavedra et al., 2016). In addition, CTS causes significant effects on plant tolerance to various stresses. Under stress conditions, CTS preserves chlorophyll content and increases flavonoid and phenolic compounds (Hidangmayum et al., 2019; Azimi et al., 2021; Sheikhalipour et al., 2021; Khalili et al., 2022). In addition, CTS plays a pivotal role as a smart carrier in delivery systems, making it highly relevant in the agricultural sector for the delivery of biostimulants (e.g., Azimi et al., 2021; Sheikhalipour et al., 2021; Gohari et al., 2021, 2023b). The use of CTS as a carrier, particularly in nanoform, results in the enhancement of controlled and sustained release, as well as greater efficiency of lower loads (Mujtaba et al., 2020; Gohari et al., 2024). Novel engineered NPs have demonstrated the capacity to enhance plant tolerance to a diverse array of stress conditions. This includes the use of CTS-selenium (Se) NPs to mitigate effects of Cd toxicity (Azimi et al., 2021) and salinity (Sheikhalipour et al., 2021), CTS-melatonin (Mel) NPs to enhance salinity tolerance (Gohari et al., 2023a), and CTS-putrescine (Put) NPs to improve Cd toxicity tolerance (Panahirad et al., 2023).

Melatonin (Mel) is a non-toxic biological compound with a multitude of fundamental functions in plant processes, including seed germination and plant senescence (Arnao and Hernandez-Ruiz, 2019). Owing to its antioxidant potency, Mel contributes to plant tolerance against various stress factors (Debnath et al., 2019; Moustafa-Farag et al., 2020) by regulating pigments, photosynthetic efficiency and indole acetic acid (IAA) content (Khan et al., 2020), reducing malondialdehyde (MDA) and ROS, triggering antioxidant enzymatic activities and regulating primary and secondary metabolism in plants (Debnath et al., 2019; Agathokleous et al., 2021). The efficacy of Mel has been particularly evident in nanoform and in combination with nanocarriers such as CTS (CTS-Mel NPs), in the alleviation of stress conditions, including salinity (e.g. Gohari et al., 2023a).

Salicylic acid is one of the most extensively researched plant growth regulators due to its pivotal roles in plant signaling and physiology, having a wide range of functions in growth and developmental pathways (Yanik et al., 2018), plant stress tolerance (Oraei et al., 2019; Gomes et al., 2021; Khalili et al., 2022), redox balance across the membranes (Mirdehghan et al., 2014) and in regulating defense enzyme activity (Dong et al., 2010; Khalili et al., 2022). Furthermore, SA increases the levels of phenolic compounds and other secondary metabolites (Oraei et al., 2019; Gomes et al., 2021) by inducing the activities of the enzymes involved, such as PAL (Dong et al., 2010; Khalili et al., 2022). In

terms of priming approaches with application potential, the use of salicylic acid as a seed priming agent has been reported in various crops for the mitigation of abiotic stress effects. For instance, Islam et al. (2022) reported that SA seed priming in baby corn significantly enhanced root dry matter, cob yield, leaf relative water content (LRWC), and proline content under salinity stress. Furthermore, according to Chakma et al. (2021), salicylic acid seed priming not only improved tomato fruit quality, but also resulted in a 33 % increase in fruit yield compared with controls under drought stress. In addition, exploiting SA in nanoform and in combination with nanocarriers, especially CTS, lead to promising effects regarding secondary metabolite biosynthesis and alleviating stress conditions (e.g., Khalili et al., 2022; Aazami et al., 2023), thus justifying increased interest for further studies of CTS-SA NPs under stress conditions.

Previously, CTS-Mel NPs were synthesized and applied foliarly as a priming agent in spearmint plants in order to mitigate the adverse effects of salinity. The use of CTS-Mel NP as a priming agent resulted in improvements in morphological traits, proline content, antioxidant enzymatic activities and the composition of the essential oil profile (Gohari et al., 2023a). Similarly, CTS-SA NPs were formulated and tested in plants under salt stress conditions, with results demonstrating that CTS-SA NPs enhanced plant growth, elevated antioxidant enzymatic activities, and augmented ROS scavenging (Khalili et al., 2022; Aazami et al., 2023). CTS-Mel NPs and CTS-SA NPs demonstrated more efficient delivery of melatonin, SA and CTS, due to their nano-size and CTS acting as a carrier, resulting in sustained release of Mel and SA and enhanced efficacy.

In light of the distinct beneficial effects of CTS, Mel and SA on various plant processes, as well as their positive impacts in conjugated nanoforms (CTS-Mel NPs and CTS-SA NPs) when applied at plant level, the current study aimed to investigate the physiological, biochemical and chemical changes that occur following the application of CTS-Mel NPs and CTS-SA NPs as seed priming agents on corn salad (*Valerianella locusta*) seedlings subjected to salt stress.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Plant materials, treatments and experimental design

Corn salad (*Valerianella locusta*) seeds were sterilized with sodium hypochlorite (for 5 min) and then washed with distilled water for three times. The seeds were subsequently primed with water (hydro-primed), CTS NPs (0.1 % w/v), Mel (50 μ M), SA (0.5 mM), CTS-Mel NPs (50 μ M) and CTS-SA NPs (0.5 mM) through soaking for 12 h (25 °C); the primed seeds were planted in 3-L pot and afterwards placed in a growth chamber. Irrigation was done using distilled water every three days until three-leaf stage. At that point, salt stress (0, 30 and 60 mM NaCl) was imposed through watering every three days, while the medium was washed every five days by applying distilled water. Sampling was done after three weeks following salinity application, in which time the plants were at five- or six- true leaf stage. Each treatment contained eight replications. The control seeds were not primed with any of the treatments (untreated or unprimed) and placed in 3-L pots with same medium and conditions; watering, salinity applications and sampling were performed in the same manner. The present experiment was conducted as a factorial experiment using a completely randomized design (CRD) with eight replications. Three replications were set for each measurement. CTS-Mel NPs and CTS-SA NPs were prepared following the protocols described by Gohari et al. (2023a) and Khalili et al. (2022), respectively.

2.2. Morphological traits, and photosynthetic pigment parameters

Leaf fresh (FW) and dry (DW) weights were assayed as morphological traits. Five leaves were weighed for FW and then kept in the oven (70 °C, 72 h) for DW measurements. Photosynthetic pigments, including

chlorophyll (chl) *a*, chl *b* and carotenoids, were measured after homogenization of leaf samples with 80 % (v/v) acetone solution, centrifuging (6000 rpm, 10 min) and spectrophotometry at 663 (chl *a*), 645 (chl *b*) and 470 (carotenoids) nm by UV-Vis spectrophotometry (UV-1800, Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan) (Lichtenthaler, 1987). A SPAD-meter (SPAD-502 Plus Chlorophyll Meter, Konica Minolta Optics, Japan) was used to determine SPAD values (leaf chlorophyll concentrations) of five randomly selected leaves in each pot.

2.3. Malondialdehyde (MDA) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂)

To assay MDA content, leaf samples (0.1 g) were extracted with acetic acid (2.5 mL; 10 % w/v) and centrifuged (15,000 rpm, 20 min). The obtained supernatants were mixed with thiobarbituric acid (0.5 % w/v) in trichloroacetic acid (TCA) (20 %) (1:1) in the test tube (96 °C, 30 min). Afterwards, extracts were placed at 0 °C (5 min) and then centrifuged (10,000 rpm, 5 min). Finally, the absorbance was measured at 532 and 600 nm by spectrophotometry and converted to MDA content according to Stewart and Bewley (1980). To quantify content of H₂O₂, leaf samples (0.2 g) were extracted with TCA (2 mL, 0.1 %) and centrifuged (12,000 rpm, 15 min). Potassium-phosphate buffer (0.5 mL, 10 mM, pH = 7.0) and KI (1 mL, 1 M) were added to the obtained supernatants (0.5 mL), and the absorbance of the mixtures was recorded at 390 nm using a spectrophotometer. The data were converted to H₂O₂ content according to Sinha et al. (2005).

2.4. Proline

Leaf samples (0.2 g) were extracted with H₂SO₄ (10 mL, 3 %) and then centrifuged (13,000 rpm, 10 min). Next, the obtained supernatants were mixed with acid-ninhydrin and glacial acetic acid (1:1:1) and placed in a water bath (100 °C, 1 h). After cooling down in ice bath, toluene (4 mL) was added to the mixture and the absorbance of final solution was read at 520 nm by spectrophotometry and proline content was calculated according to Bates et al. (1973).

2.5. Antioxidant enzymatic activities

Leaf samples (0.2 g) were homogenized with potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) containing 1 % w/v polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVPP), 4 mM ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) and 0.05 % Triton X-100 through ice cold extraction and then centrifuged (13,000 rpm, 15 min, 4 °C). The obtained supernatants were used to measure the activity of superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT) antioxidant enzymes based on the methods described by Jiang and Zhang (2002). Protein content was determined according to Bradford (1976).

2.6. Phenolic compounds

Leaf samples (0.1 g) were extracted with ethanol (5 mL, 95 %), placed in dark (24 h) and centrifuged. The obtained supernatant (1 mL) was mixed with ethanol (1 mL, 95 %), distilled water (3 mL), Folin-Ciocalteu solution (0.5 mL, 50 %) and sodium bicarbonate (1 mL, 5 %) and kept in the dark (1 h). Finally, the absorbance was recorded at 725 nm using a spectrophotometer. Phenolic content was calculated based on the standard curve obtained by different concentrations of gallic acid (Xu et al., 2010).

Phenolic profiles of extracts were additionally examined by HPLC. The leaf samples were kept frozen at -20 °C until further analysis. In order to quantify the phenolic compounds, the plant samples were firstly subjected to a shaker-assisted sequential extraction (Celikcan et al., 2021). Briefly, 3 g of plant material was extracted with 50 ml of methanol at 120 rpm for 24 h at room temperature. The extraction process was repeated on three separate occasions with the same plant materials in order to collect all residual materials following the extraction procedure. A rotary evaporator (Heidolph 94,200, Bioblock Scientific) was

used to evaporate the filtrates of three extractions. The vacuo-dried samples were preserved at +4 °C until chromatographic analysis.

2.7. High-Performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) analysis of phenolic compounds

The samples were filtered through 0.45 µm filter discs prior to HPLC analysis. The analysis was carried at Igdır University Research Laboratory Application and Research Center (ALUM). An HPLC system (Agilent LC 1260-AB Sciex API 5500, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with a diode array detector was used. The mobile phases employed were as follows: (A) 0.1 % phosphoric acid in water and (B) HPLC-grade 100 % acetonitrile. The quantity of phenolics was determined by comparing the peaks observed at 300 nm with the standard curves for each acid (Kalili and Villiers, 2011).

2.8. Data analysis

The average values corresponding to the treatments were subjected to ANOVA assumption using Shapiro-Wilk and Levene tests. The average values were separated using Duncan's *post-hoc* test at 0.05 significance level (SPSS 26). In addition to the variance analysis, correlation analysis (JASP, v. 0.16), principal component analysis (PAST) and network-plot analysis (PAST) were carried out to associate, cluster and reduce the dimension of the variables.

3. Results

3.1. Biomass

As expected, salinity (60 mM NaCl) decreased the FW, whereas both levels of salinity (30 and 60 mM NaCl) similarly reduced DW (Table 1). FW values were not significantly affected by any of the treatments under control and 30 mM NaCl conditions. The FW values were observed to increase under 60 mM NaCl salt stress, following the application of Mel and CTS-Mel NP treatments. Only the CTS-Mel NPs increased the DW values at 30 mM NaCl, while none of the treatments had any effect on DW at 60 mM NaCl.

3.2. Pigments

Chl *a*, total Chl and SPAD values were reduced by salinity at 60 mM NaCl (Table 1). However, salt stress did not affect the levels of chl *b*, chl *a/b* and carotenoids. With regard to the exogenous applications, it was observed that SA, Mel, CTS-SA NP and CTS-Mel NP treatments lead to an enhancement of chl *a* values under control conditions. In the case of 30 mM NaCl, CTS-SA NPs and CTS-Mel NPs increased chl *a* content. On the other hand, Mel and CTS-Mel NPs caused a significantly higher chl *a* content at 60 mM NaCl stress. For chl *b*, none of the treatments affected its levels under control conditions, whereas CTS-Mel NPs and CTS NPs increased chl *b* levels under 30 and 60 mM NaCl salinity, respectively. Under 60 mM NaCl stress, Mel and CTS-Mel NP treatments significantly increased its content, while the treatments had no effect in chl *a/b* values under either control or salinity conditions. The results showed that CTS-SA and CTS-Mel NPs increased plant carotenoid content under control conditions. Furthermore, CTS NPs increased carotenoids under 60 mM NaCl salt stress. SPAD values were elevated by the application of CTS-SA NPs and CTS-Mel NPs under control conditions, Mel and CTS-SA NPs under 30 mM NaCl stress, and CTS NPs, SA, Mel, CTS-SA NPs and CTS-Mel NPs under 60 mM NaCl stress.

3.3. Cellular stress markers

Under control conditions, none of the treatments had a significant effect in MDA content. Under 30 mM NaCl stress, Hydro, Mel, CTS-SA NP and CTS-Mel NP-primed plants had lowed MDA content, as did

Table 1Effects of melatonin and salicylic acid-functionalized chitosan seed priming in physiological and biochemical attributes in *Valerianella locusta* L. seedlings under salinity stress.

Treatments	FW	DW	SPAD	Chl a	Chl b	Total Chl	Chl a/b	Carotenoids	MDA	H ₂ O ₂	Proline	Protein	SOD	CAT	Total Phenolics	
Control	Unprimed	11.78 abc	1.86 b	56.33 b-e	4.01 bc	1.00 c-e	5.01 a-d	4.41 a-e	0.39 c-e	21.69 ef	64.90 a	2.62 f	2.52 f	2.60 f	1.26 e	116.92 f
	Hydroprimed	13.60 a	1.98 ab	63.47 ab	4.02 bc	1.26 b-d	5.28 a-d	3.18 c-f	0.54 a-d	17.55 f	69.72 a	3.10 ef	1.99 f	3.14 def	2.14 de	108.81 f
	Chitosan NPs	11.27 bcd	1.82 b	57.74 a-e	4.22 a-c	0.80 c-e	5.02 a-d	5.27 a-c	0.23 e	19.68 f	60.99 ab	4.62 def	2.47 f	2.69 ef	1.83 e	160.36 c-e
	Salicylic acid	13.05 ab	1.83 b	61.30 abc	5.59 a	0.94 c-e	6.52 a	6.10 a	0.36 de	19.38 f	48.58 c-f	4.64 def	2.28 f	2.74 ef	1.07 e	159.48 c-e
	Melatonin	14.39 a	2.19 a	59.80 a-d	5.75 a	1.18 b-e	6.93 a	5.12 a-c	0.47 b-e	17.46 f	45.14 ef	5.79 b-e	2.96 f	3.64 c-f	2.50 de	156.52 de
	Chitosan-salicylic acid NPs	13.11 ab	0.96 d	64.27 a	5.91 a	0.84 c-e	6.75 a	7.00 a	0.69 ab	19.45 f	46.58 ef	5.82 b-e	2.55 f	3.74 c-f	1.07 e	151.10 e
	Chitosan-melatonin NPs	14.14 a	0.82 def	66.23 a	7.22 a	1.33 bc	8.55 a	5.76 ab	0.78 a	18.86 f	43.37 f	5.62 c-e	2.98 f	3.59 def	1.83 e	172.69 a-e
	30 mM NaCl	Unprimed	10.60 cd	0.89 de	50.70 e	3.45 cd	1.29 b-d	4.74 b-d	2.66 def	0.48 b-e	33.55 d	70.21 a	5.46 c-e	2.29 f	3.81 c-f	1.64 e
Hydroprimed		11.43 bc	0.86 def	50.83 e	3.08 c-e	1.06 b-e	4.13 c-f	2.89 def	0.40 c-e	23.54 ef	58.10 abc	6.43 a-d	2.30 f	4.18 b-e	1.43 e	150.31 e
Chitosan NPs		10.81 cd	0.94 d	51.93 e	3.21 c-e	1.15 b-e	4.36 c-e	2.81 def	0.42 c-e	30.01 de	57.13 a-d	5.66 c-e	2.65 f	3.45 d-f	1.67 e	153.56 e
Salicylic acid		11.45 bc	0.77 def	56.37 b-e	3.02 c-e	0.70 e	3.72 c-f	4.58 a-d	0.24 e	24.95 def	54.89 a-e	7.29 a-d	2.51 f	5.15 a-c	1.57 e	166.67 b-e
Melatonin		11.56 bc	0.99 de	59.77 a-d	3.93 bc	1.14 b-e	5.07 a-d	3.83 b-e	0.42 c-e	21.79 ef	52.78 b-f	7.96 a-c	2.07 f	5.60 ab	3.35 cd	176.73 a-d
Chitosan-salicylic acid NPs		9.45 de	0.94 d	62.10 ab	4.92 ab	1.28 b-d	6.20 ab	3.94 b-e	0.48 b-e	22.54 ef	44.04 f	7.75 a-c	4.04 f	6.64 a	3.29 cd	183.63 ab
Chitosan-melatonin NPs		11.93 abc	1.28 c	54.40 c-e	5.68 a	2.07 a	7.74 a	2.75 def	0.64 a-c	23.15 ef	47.32 d-f	7.82 a-c	5.64 cd	4.65 a-d	3.50 cd	160.86 c-e
60 mM NaCl		Unprimed	6.35 f	0.61 ef	39.54 f	2.04 d-f	0.84 c-e	2.88 ef	2.42 ef	0.34 de	66.35 a	95.70 a	7.80 a-c	5.25 d	7.30 a	3.98 c
	Hydroprimed	7.35 f	0.73 def	36.80 f	1.47 f	1.09 b-e	2.56 f	1.46 f	0.46 b-e	63.26 a	102.21 a	8.64 a	6.02 cd	8.21 a	5.40 b	187.67 ab
	Chitosan NPs	7.69 ef	0.59 f	54.23 c-e	1.97 ef	1.58 b	3.54 def	1.24 f	0.63 a-c	72.23 a	89.77 a	7.86 a-c	5.43 d	5.74 a	5.92 b	170.73 a-e
	Salicylic acid	7.85 ef	0.80 def	53.93 c-e	2.07 def	0.78 de	2.85 ef	2.85 def	0.23 e	60.56 ab	81.89 a	8.49 ab	6.64 c	7.03 a	7.37 a	181.26 a-c
	Melatonin	9.43 de	0.81 def	52.93 de	3.89 bc	1.03 c-e	4.92 a-d	3.92 b-e	0.41 c-e	51.31 bc	67.91 a	12.90 a	10.32 a	8.81 a	8.44 a	176.82 a-d
	Chitosan-salicylic acid NPs	7.67 ef	0.69 def	51.10 e	3.37 c-e	1.01 c-e	4.39 c-e	3.31 c-f	0.39 c-e	59.69 ab	80.80 a	10.82 a	7.88 b	9.58 a	8.57 a	190.03 a
	Chitosan-melatonin NPs	10.12 cd	0.81 def	58.40 a-e	4.27 a-c	1.12 b-e	5.39 a-c	4.20 a-e	0.50 b-e	46.90 c	57.52 a-d	12.84 a	10.95 a	10.82 a	7.40 b	195.85 a
	p-values	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

*The assessment is based on the average values of the treatments. Red color indicates higher values, while blue color indicates lower values. Means with the same letter are not significantly different from each other ($p > 0.05$)

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Mel and CTS-Mel NP-primed plants under 60 mM NaCl stress (Fig. 1A). Under control conditions, the application of SA, Mel, CTS-SA NPs and CTS-Mel NPs reduced H₂O₂ levels. In the presence of 30 mM NaCl, priming with Mel, CTS-SA NPs and CTS-Mel NPs resulted in a significant reduction in H₂O₂ levels. In contrast, under 60 mM NaCl, no treatment had an effect on H₂O₂ content under 60 mM NaCl (Fig. 1B).

Proline content was observed to increase under salt stress conditions. However, no statistically significant differences were identified between the various levels of salt stress. Mel, CTS-SA NPs and CTS-Mel NPs caused a significant increase in proline levels under control conditions, while none of the treatments affected proline levels at 30 and 60 mM NaCl (Fig. 2A).

3.4. Enzymatic antioxidants

Application of 60 mM NaCl was found to enhance the activities of SOD and CAT in Mel and CTS-SA NP treatments. In contrast, under control conditions, none of the treatments affected the activities of SOD and CAT (Fig. 3A and B). In the case of 30 mM NaCl stress, the activity of SOD increased with the treatment of Mel and CTS-SA NPs. However, at 60 mM NaCl, the activity of SOD was affected by all treatments (Fig. 3A). Application of Mel, CTS-SA NP and CTS-Mel NP priming treatments resulted in a significant increase in CAT activity at 30 mM NaCl. The application of all treatments, including hydro-, CTS NPs-, SA-, Mel-, CTS-SA NP and CTS-Mel NP priming agents, resulted in an increase in CAT activity. The highest level of activity was observed in the SA, Mel and CTS-SA NP priming treatments (Fig. 3B).

3.5. Phenolic compound profile

Salinity (at both 30 and 60 mM NaCl) led to an increase in total

phenolic content across all treatments compared with the control. Both levels of salinity were statistically similar. CTS NPs, SA, Mel, CTS-SA NP and CTS-Mel NP priming treatments caused an increase in content under control conditions (Fig. 4A). Priming with Mel and CTS-SA NPs increased total phenolics under 30 mM NaCl stress, while CTS-SA and CTS-Mel NPs increased phenolics under 60 mM NaCl stress (Fig. 4A).

As presented in Table 2, seventeen phenolic compounds were quantified. Chlorogenic acid was found to be the dominant compound, followed by naringin, o-coumaric acid, catechine hydrate, resveratrol, and t-cinnamic acid. The most abundant phenolic compound, chlorogenic acid, was not significantly affected by salt stress (Fig. 4B). Mel and CTS-Mel NPs increased the levels of chlorogenic acid under control conditions, CTS-SA NPs and CTS-Mel NPs increased chlorogenic acid levels at 30 mM NaCl, and only CTS-Mel NP treatment increased its content at 60 mM NaCl. For naringin, the second most abundant component of the phenolic profile of corn salad, salinity increased its content with both salinity levels acting in a statistically similar manner. The application of CTS-Mel NP priming treatments increased naringin content under control and both salt stress levels (Table 2). The content of o-coumaric acid was positively affected by SA, Mel and CTS-Mel NP priming treatments under control conditions, CTS NPs, SA and CTS-Mel NPs under 30 mM NaCl and CTS-Mel NPs under 60 mM NaCl (Table 2). Catechine hydrate was increased by CTS-Mel NP application under control and 30 mM NaCl, while none of the treatments affected its content under 60 mM NaCl. Resveratrol was not affected by any of the treatments under control and both salinity conditions. t-Cinnamic acid was enhanced by SA and CTS-SA NPs application under control conditions, whereas none of the treatments enhanced its content under 30 and 60 mM NaCl salinity levels (Table 2).

Fig. 1. Effects of melatonin and salicylic acid-functionalized chitosan seed priming in MDA (A) and H_2O_2 (B) contents in *Valerianella locusta* under salinity stress. Mean values \pm SE ($n = 3$). Different letters show significant differences at $p \leq 0.05$.

3.6. PCA and network plot analysis

Due to the large number of variables (parameters and treatments), in addition to the one-way variance analysis, two other analyses were performed, including principal component analysis (PCA) and network plot analysis. In order to explain the variation ratio, biochemical and physiological attributes considered for analysis were scattered on a biplot pair (Fig. 5). Accordingly, two first components (PC_1 : 54.5 % and PC_2 : 19.15 %) accounted for 73.65 % of the variability of the original data. Concerning the components, the first component (PC_1) was negatively correlated with the MDA, H_2O_2 , proline, SOD, CAT, and total phenolics, whereas the component was positively correlated with the FW, DW, chl, a/b. On the other hand, the second component (PC_2) was found to be positively correlated with proline, SOD, CAT, and total phenolics. The first component can be considered as photosynthetic components and yield parameters, while the second component can be regarded as stress indices and antioxidant defense system. With respect

Fig. 2. Effects of melatonin and salicylic acid-functionalized chitosan seed priming in proline content in *Valerianella locusta* under salinity stress. Mean values \pm SE ($n = 3$). Different letters show significant differences at $p \leq 0.05$.

to the scattering of the treatments, a clear discrimination was observed on the biplot pair. First component included the stress-free conditions (S0 : Control) and the second component was mostly characterized by the high-level salinity conditions (S60 : 60 mM NaCl). For consolidating the effects of the treatments in the plants, the link between each treatment based on the performance/effects on the physiological and biochemical attributes considered for analysis was revealed using network plot analysis (Fig. 6). The similarities or dissimilarities of the treatments are associated with thinner/lighter and thicker lines. Network plot analysis also clearly revealed the sharp differences between control and 30 mM NaCl stress groups and 60 mM NaCl stress groups. Overall, the present findings revealed that treatments can be effective in combating low level of salinity. In addition to the physiological and biochemical attributes, we further performed similar analysis for phenolic compounds. Concerning PCA analysis of phenolic compounds, a total of 46.7 % (PC_1 : 30.81 % and PC_2 : 15.89 %) for the variability of the original data was explained (Fig. 7). Such a low-level ratio might not be effective in explaining the responses of the phenolics corresponding to the treatments. In accordance with PCA, network plot analysis also did not discriminate the performances/effects of the treatments on the phenolics analyzed here (Fig. 8). Of the major compounds, chlorogenic acid was positively correlated with the first component (PC_1). PC_1 was positively correlated with S0-Mel , S0-CTS-Mel , S30-CTS , S30-CTS-SA , S60-Mel , and S60-CTS-Mel .

4. Discussion

Salinity stress results in an imbalance in ion homeostasis, with an increase in Na^+ and Cl^- ions. This leads to osmotic stress, which subsequently reduces water and nutrient uptake, ultimately affecting plant growth parameters (Gohari et al., 2023a). Accordingly, the observed decrease in FW and DW under the salinity conditions of the current study is consistent with numerous previous reports (e.g., Gohari et al., 2023a; Sheikhalipour et al., 2023, 2024). The application of SA and CTS-SA NPs resulted in an increase in the FW and DW of grape berries, which can be attributed to the role of SA in cell division and enlargement, as well as its impact on water and nutrient uptake (Khalili et al., 2022). However, SA and CTS-SA NPs were not effective in FW and DW in the current study. The differences between plant species, salinity levels and treatment concentrations might explain the ineffectiveness in corn salad. Mel has auxin-like effects that enhance plant growth and

Fig. 3. Effects of melatonin and salicylic acid-functionalized chitosan seed priming in SOD (A) and CAT (B) enzymatic activities in *Valerianella locusta* under salinity stress. Mean values \pm SE ($n = 3$). Different letters show significant differences at $p \leq 0.05$.

additionally confer tolerance to stress conditions such as salinity (Arnao and Hernandez-Ruiz, 2019). This is probably due to an improvement in water and nutrient uptake and a reduction in Na⁺ and Cl⁻ accumulation (Moustafa-Farag et al., 2020). For example, the application of Mel to salt-stressed plants resulted in enhanced morphological traits, including FW and DW (Sheikhalipour et al., 2024).

Similarly, it has been demonstrated that CTS can enhance the uptake of water, nutrients and essential elements, particularly in plants subjected to salt stress (Hidangmayum et al., 2019). Furthermore, CTS has been shown to stimulate the production of polyamines in plants, which in turn promote growth and enhances stress tolerance (Geng et al., 2020). It was demonstrated that Mel and CTS, when used individually and in combination, were able to neutralise the salinity effect in plant growth reduction (Hidangmayum et al., 2019; Gohari et al., 2023a). The application of CTS-Mel NPs has been demonstrated to have a positive effect in certain growth parameters of plants under stress conditions (Gohari et al., 2023a). These facts could describe the effects of Mel and,

Fig. 4. Effects of melatonin and salicylic acid-functionalized chitosan seed priming in total phenolics (A) and chlorogenic acid (B) content in *Valerianella locusta* under salinity stress. Mean values \pm SE ($n = 3$). Different letters show significant differences at $p \leq 0.05$.

more importantly, CTS-Mel NPs leading to higher FW and DW, especially under salinity, most likely by improving water, macro- and micro-nutrient uptake and cell division and proliferation via their hormonal-like effects.

Photosynthetic pigments are essential for photosynthesis and subsequently plant performance and metabolism (Wungrampha et al., 2018), with salinity mostly reducing their content through stomatal closure, decrease in carbon assimilation, photooxidation (Gohari et al., 2023a; Sheikhalipour et al., 2023, 2024) and absorption of essential elements for chl structure (e.g., Mg²⁺) through the reaction of Na⁺ with ion exchange channels (Moustafa-Farag et al., 2020). Considering the present results, chl a, total chl and SPAD were negatively affected by salinity, consistent with previous observations; it is likely that salinity levels were not at the threshold to be destructive to chl b and carotenoid contents. SA and CTS-SA NPs caused increase in carotenoid content in grapevine (Khalili et al., 2022). CTS-SA NPs increased Chl a and chl b content under control conditions, and total chl and carotenoids under salinity conditions (Aazami et al., 2023), somewhat in line with current

Table 2
Effects of melatonin and salicylic acid-functionalized chitosan seed priming in phenolic compound profile in *Valerianella locusta* under salinity stress.

Treatments	Chlorogenic acid	Catechine hydrate	Caffeic acid	4-Hydroxy benzoic acid	Vanillin	p-Coumaric acid	Rutin	t-Ferulic acid	Hydroxy sinamic acid	Naringin	o-Coumaric acid	Rosmarinic acid	Salicylic acid	Resveratrol	Quercetin	t-Cinnamic acid	Naringenin
Control																	
Unprimed	45,89	3,49	2,04	1,60	0,00	1,18	0,00	1,25	1,90	11,36	3,90	2,23	0,69	3,20	1,43	3,08	0,73
Hydroprimed	73,25	4,28	3,88	5,43	3,58	5,57	0,00	3,56	5,03	16,80	5,94	5,00	2,83	2,17	1,91	8,05	0,73
Chitosan NPs	71,53	5,58	4,85	5,16	3,06	1,33	1,25	4,69	5,48	27,99	6,77	4,84	2,84	3,91	1,45	6,79	2,40
Salicylic acid	97,46	0,00	1,52	8,77	0,43	2,64	0,41 c	1,20	5,69	39,27	9,73	6,55	8,40	2,01	2,83	12,70	1,59
Melatonin	148,28	3,38	0,93	6,96	6,37	5,12	0,00	5,95	3,56	49,24	9,74	4,40	0,40	3,65	1,82	8,01	0,00
Chitosan-salicylic acid NPs	110,58	7,07	4,03	5,11	6,82	3,20	0,00	6,80	2,68	34,72	7,21	4,97	4,94	1,91	2,26	10,09	1,75
Chitosan-melatonin NPs	147,27	17,01	2,62	2,27	6,01	4,64	4,06	0,76	2,48	62,86	9,15	6,30	4,78	5,12	1,92	6,75	3,47
30 mM NaCl																	
Unprimed	30,78	1,64	0,00	4,59	0,00	1,63	0,00	0,69	5,25	16,42	3,05	2,80	1,27	2,99	3,43	6,38	2,41
Hydroprimed	80,36	0,00	1,77	5,60	2,96	4,11	0,00	4,03	4,74	45,24	6,87	6,68	1,74	4,68	2,65	8,85	5,19
Chitosan NPs	91,70	0,00	4,41	6,24	2,99	5,27	1,22	1,82	1,25	51,40	8,94	5,12	2,73	4,41	2,83	10,83	6,11
Salicylic acid	115,18	0,00	5,46	5,84	3,30	3,10	0,00	2,81	6,45	61,09	8,48	4,48	4,42	2,09	2,16	11,53	1,86
Melatonin	110,21	10,30	4,30	4,38	0,38	7,22	0,58	1,92	2,70	25,17	6,92	3,08	5,39	5,22	2,72	9,02	5,59
Chitosan-salicylic acid NPs	135,01	0,00	6,51	5,95	1,52	6,40	2,17	3,12	0,76	49,67	5,58	3,15	5,02	3,80	4,35	10,00	3,46
Chitosan-melatonin NPs	206,79	14,31	7,39	1,34	0,44	4,19	0,54	2,95	1,23	74,47	8,85	5,60	9,27	2,03	1,72	13,04	5,18
60 mM NaCl																	
Unprimed	77,11	2,58	0,00	8,15	4,08	4,85	0,54	4,30	3,01	21,34	5,73	3,67	2,57	3,25	1,23	9,18	2,67
Hydroprimed	46,57	1,13	0,58	3,24	0,00	1,75	0,00	0,40	4,89	7,80	2,51	5,06	1,00	2,46	5,06	3,64	1,57
Chitosan NPs	88,62	2,58	0,98	5,71	2,86	3,48	0,00	3,31	5,24	20,33	4,87	6,57	3,55	3,22	1,31	7,48	2,24
Salicylic acid	106,53	3,17	4,46	3,00	4,30	3,71	0,00	1,08	5,01	12,65	4,33	3,77	2,12	3,32	9,17	8,56	6,20
Melatonin	163,97	11,21	0,00	3,99	3,07	6,93	3,06	3,31	3,81	55,09	6,08	3,78	5,04	1,36	1,39	8,46	2,57
Chitosan-salicylic acid NPs	116,85	4,22	0,00	5,78	2,60	3,25	0,00	4,55	2,65	35,25	5,41	2,62	2,37	3,42	3,92	8,17	0,69
Chitosan-melatonin NPs	274,28	5,86	1,96	3,83	4,42	3,01	0,79	2,90	3,50	93,14	11,15	2,94	5,30	2,89	3,58	12,50	2,53

*The assessment is based on the average values of the treatments. Red color indicates higher values, while blue color indicates lower values.

*The assessment is based on the average values of the treatments. Red color indicates higher values, while blue color indicates lower values.

Fig. 5. Principal component analysis of the examined physiological and biochemical attributes.

chl a findings (control and 30 mM salinity), carotenoids (control) and SPAD (control and both salinity conditions). Mel could positively affect stomatal size, inhibit stomatal closure, and improve gas exchange, thus resulting in better carbon assimilation and carbohydrate accumulation (Kanwar et al., 2018). Furthermore, Mel inhibits photooxidation and maintains membrane stability of cells and structures (e.g., chloroplasts) (Zhan et al., 2019). Mel causes reduction in ROS generation by

increasing antioxidant capacity and enzymatic activities, decreasing oxidative stress in plants and finally preserving chloroplast structure under stress conditions (Sheikhalipour et al., 2022). Mel application improved photosynthetic pigments, net photosynthetic rate (P_n) and maximum quantum efficiency of photosystem II (F_v/F_m) in sage plants under salt stress conditions (Sheikhalipour et al., 2024). Similarly, CTS plays a role in chlorophyll (Hidangmayum et al., 2019; Safikhan et al.,

Fig. 6. Network plot analysis of the examined physiological and biochemical attributes.

2018) and cytokinin biosynthesis (Bakhroum et al., 2020) that result in higher photosynthetic pigment content, especially under salinity. CTS-Mel NPs, as priming treatment, enhanced the content of photosynthetic pigments and chlorophyll fluorescence attributes under control and salinity conditions (Gohari et al., 2023a). Considering that mostly CTS-Mel NPs caused higher chl *a*, *b*, total chl and SPAD under salinity conditions, it seems that the improved photosynthetic pigment content is a result of the nano-size and improved efficiency of Mel using CTS as a carrier.

MDA and H_2O_2 content act as universal stress markers. Therefore, salinity results in their induction (Gohari et al., 2020b; Aazami et al., 2023; Sheikhalipour et al., 2023). In the current study, salinity caused increase in MDA, as expected, but had no significant effect in H_2O_2 content. It is likely that salinity at the currently applied levels mostly disrupted membranes and enhanced MDA, but stress severity was not sufficient for oxidative stress-induced H_2O_2 burst. For instance, Gohari et al. (2023a) stated that both salinity levels (50 and 100 mM NaCl)

caused increase in MDA, but only 100 mM NaCl enhanced H_2O_2 content, that could explain the current result at least in part. SA application reduced H_2O_2 and MDA content in grapevines under salinity conditions (Oraei et al., 2019). CTS-SA application reduced MDA and H_2O_2 content of grapevines under salinity conditions (Aazami et al., 2023). CTS application could also directly decrease MDA content in plants under stress conditions (Hidangmayum et al., 2019; Azimi et al., 2021). Mel and CTS could additionally activate the antioxidant system by inducing antioxidant enzymes thus lowering H_2O_2 and MDA content, predominantly under salinity conditions (Hidangmayum et al., 2019; Zhan et al., 2019; Azimi et al., 2021). Furthermore, Mel was shown to lower H_2O_2 content by converting it to water and oxygen and protected plant cell membranes that caused reduction in MDA (Moustafa-Farag et al., 2020). MDA and H_2O_2 content decreased in Mel-treated plants under drought and salinity stress conditions via improvement in antioxidant enzymatic activities (Sheikhalipour et al., 2023, 2024). CTS and CTS-Se NPs decreased MDA and H_2O_2 , particularly under stress conditions (Azimi et al., 2021). CTS, Mel and CTS-Mel NPs decreased MDA under 50 mM NaCl salinity levels, while Mel and CTS-Mel NPs were effective under 100 mM NaCl stress. CTS, Mel and CTS-Mel NPs reduced H_2O_2 under control and 50 and 100 mM NaCl salinity levels (Gohari et al., 2023a). All these studies were mostly in agreement with the current results. In total, Mel, CTS-Mel NPs and CTS-SA NPs caused a decrease in MDA and H_2O_2 contents under salinity conditions, most likely via enhanced effect of CTS, SA and Mel in the nano-form, preserving membrane stability, inducing antioxidant enzymatic activities and increasing proline content, in line with the above-mentioned studies.

Proline has osmoprotective activity and accumulates in plants under hyperosmotic stress conditions such as salinity (Filippou et al., 2014; Aazami et al., 2023) to decrease osmotic pressure in cells (Munns and Tester, 2008; Van Zelm et al., 2020), as observed in the current study. SA treatment lead to enhanced proline content in grapevines under salinity conditions, probably by triggering the metabolic consumption of soluble sugars to form new constituents like proline to reduce adverse effects of salinity (Oraei et al., 2019). CTS-SA NPs enhanced proline content in grapevines under salinity conditions (Aazami et al., 2023). The role of CTS in osmolyte production was previously shown to lead to better preservation of cell turbidity and cell water balance under salinity (Hidangmayum et al., 2019). Similarly, Mel caused increase in proline

Fig. 7. Principal component analysis of phenolic compounds.

article.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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